

Azine Dyes as Iodometric Indicators*

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The use of two azine dyes, Wool Fast Blue BL and Wool Fast Blue GL as iodometric indicators is reported.

THE first indicator that was suggested in titrations involving iodine was starch, which produces an intense blue colour with iodine, due to the formation of starch-iodine complex. In spite of its wide use and uniqueness in iodometric titrations, starch has the following shortcomings: (1) insolubility in cold water, (2) instability of its aqueous dispersions, and (3) need for addition towards the close of the titration. Consequently, several workers have reported modifications of starch including soluble starch solutions.

During recent times the following dyes have also been employed as iodometric indicators:

Dye(s)	Reference
Variamine Blue	Erdey and co-workers ¹
Methylene Blue	Gautier ²
Malachite Green	Meditsch ³
Basic Blue 11, Basic Blue 15, Basic Blue 20 and Basic Violet 4	Brazier and Stephen ⁴
Setoglauanine O and Setocyanine Supra	Venkateswara Rao and Eswara Dutt ⁵

We have observed that two azine dyes, Wool Fast Blue BL (WFBBL) and Wool Fast Blue GL (WFBGL) (Colour index Nos. 50315 and 50320 respectively) function very satisfactorily as indicators in the iodine-thiosulphate or iodine-arsenic(III) titrations or *vice versa*. The advantages of the present indicators are: (1) ease of preparation of indicator solution, (2) stability of their aqueous solutions and consequent retention of indicator action for longer periods, (3) addition even at the beginning of the titration, and (4) suitability in the presence of about 20% sodium chloride and 50% ethanol.

Experimental

Reagents. 0.1 N solutions of iodine (in 2% potassium iodide) and sodium thiosulphate were prepared

and standardised. 0.1 N solution of arsenic(III) was prepared from Merck 'pro analysi' sample of arsenious oxide.

0.1% solutions of the dyes, Wool Fast Blue BL and Wool Fast Blue GL were prepared in doubly distilled water. We are grateful to M/S Bayer AG, Leverkusen, Germany, for gifts of these two dye samples which are manufactured under the trade names: "Supranol Blue BL ex conc." and "Supranol Blue GL 200%" respectively. These samples were used without further purification.

All other reagents used in this investigation were of reagent grade quality.

Procedure. An aliquot volume of 0.1 N iodine solution is taken into a 250 ml iodine flask and diluted to 50 ml. 0.1 ml of 0.1% WFBBL or WFBGL is then added and the mixture is titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate and the end point of the titration is taken as that at which the colour sharply changes from colourless to blue in both cases.

Iodine can be titrated with arsenic(III) using the two indicators provided about 1 g of sodium bicarbonate is added to the titration mixture before commencing the titration, to maintain the pH between 5 and 9.

The reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of thiosulphate or arsenic(III) with iodine can also be carried out under the same conditions of direct titrations; however, the end point in this case is from blue to colourless.

Titration in dilute solutions. In the titration of 0.01 N iodine solutions with 0.01 N solutions of thiosulphate or arsenic(III) using these two indicators, satisfactory end points are not obtained. But sharp end points are obtained in titrations involving 0.025 N solutions. The same observation has been made in the case of titration of thiosulphate or arsenic(III) with iodine. In these titrations, a blank correction of 0.03-0.04 ml of the titrant should be applied for 0.1 ml of 0.1% WFBBL or WFBGL.

The results obtained are given in Table 1.

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TABLE I—TITRATION OF IODINE WITH THIOSULPHATE AND ARSENIC(III) AND VICE VERSA USING WOOL FAST BLUE BL AND WOOL FAST BLUE GL AS INDICATORS

Titration	Amount of substance taken, mmoles	Amount of substance found, mmoles	
		WFBBL method	WFBGL method
	Iodine :		
Iodine-thiosulphate	0.0750	0.07525	0.07474
	0.2250	0.2254	0.2254
	0.5000	0.5012	0.5013
	0.9000	0.9034	0.9022
	Iodine :		
Iodine-arsenic(III)	0.0750	0.0750	0.0751
	0.2250	0.2242	0.2253
	0.5000	0.5014	0.5008
	0.9000	0.9026	0.9034
	Thiosulphate :		
Thiosulphate-iodine	0.0789	0.0787	0.0788
	0.1315	0.1310	0.1313
	0.4400	0.4400	0.4410
	0.7920	0.7903	0.7920
	Arsenic(III) :		
Arsenic(III)-iodine	0.0735	0.0733	0.0730
	0.1225	0.1220	0.1225
	0.4830	0.4820	0.4821
	0.8694	0.8680	0.8676

Discussion

In his studies on the use of Methylene Blue as iodometric indicator, Gautier² has shown that iodine decolourises Methylene Blue forming the hydroiodide of tetraiodo Methylene Blue, a brown precipitate. He has also shown that this brown precipitate reacts with thiosulphate or arsenic(III) and regenerates the Methylene Blue. The indicator (iodometric) action of Malachite Green has also been explained to be due to a similar mechanism³. But we could not observe the formation of a precipitate in the case of the dyes of the present investigation. This aspect is under further investigation.

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